

Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) analysis of damage in fiber-reinforced composites

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Outline

- Preliminary DVC analyses (checking the measurement error)
 - Duplicated image
 - Translated image
 - Digitally deformed image
- DVC of real deformation
 - Full-size damage analysis (whole specimen) → ply-level
 - Detailed damage analysis → micro-level
 - Damage interaction
 - Crack analysis

Specimen and imaging

- $[90_4, 0_{10}, 90_4]$
- Carbon/epoxy
- Autoclaved
- Double-notched

- Tension in 0° (Z-)direction
- *In-situ* synchrotron micro-CT
- Voxel size: $1.1^3 \mu\text{m}^3$

DVC

- DVC is performed using the Avizo (2019.1) software
- DVC can be done using two algorithms in Avizo: local and global
- The displacement field calculated in the local approach is used as an initial guess for the global approach.

subset-based (**local**)
coarse cubic mesh $\sim 53 \mu\text{m}$

finite-element based (**global**)
fine tetrahedral mesh $\sim 18 \mu\text{m}$

Duplicated-image DVC

- Applying DVC to a 3D image (region of interest) and its **duplicate**
- The resulting **strain mean** and **standard deviation** can be assessed to check the accuracy and precision of the DVC analysis.

Longitudinal ply

Transverse ply

DVC resulting values

Applied translation/strain	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Transverse strain mean (%)	Transverse strain STD (%)
0	0	0	0	0

Applied translation/strain	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Transverse strain mean (%)	Transverse strain STD (%)
0	0	0.003	0	0.001

Translated-image DVC

- Applying DVC to a 3D image and its **translated duplicate** (in the axial and transverse directions)

Longitudinal ply

Transverse ply

Applied translation/strain	Disp. mean (px)	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Trans. strain mean (%)	Trans. strain STD (%)
10 px long. translation	3.130	0.096	3.002	0.041	0.692
10 px trans. translation	9.000	0	0	0	0

Applied translation/strain	Disp. mean (px)	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Trans. strain mean (%)	Trans. strain STD (%)
10 px long. translation	9.998	-0.021	0.330	0.001	0.018
10 px trans. translation	9.998	1.180	36.560	0.065	2.261

Translated-image DVC (strain fields)

- Applying DVC to a 3D image and its **translated duplicate** (in the axial and transverse directions)

Applied translation/ strain	Disp. mean (px)	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Trans. strain mean (%)	Trans. strain STD (%)
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The **bold** values correspond to the shown strain fields above.

Digitally-deformed-image DVC

- Digitally resizing the image using bilinear resampling (in the axial and transverse directions)
- Applying DVC to the 3D image and the **digitally deformed** one

Longitudinal ply

Applied translation/strain	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Transverse strain mean (%)	Transverse strain STD (%)
2% long. strain	2.014	0.572	0.001	0.015
2% trans. strain	0.018	0.078	2.02	0.097

Transverse ply

Applied translation/strain	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Transverse strain mean (%)	Transverse strain STD (%)
2% long. strain	2.020	0.103	0.0001	0.004
2% trans. strain	0.005	0.310	2.028	0.366

Digitally-deformed-image DVC (strain fields)

- Although digitally deforming the image excludes some physical errors and adds some false errors, it is one of the only ways that we can apply a know deformation to the material and analyze it.

Applied translation/strain	Long. strain mean (%)	Long. strain STD (%)	Transverse strain mean (%)	Transverse strain STD (%)
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Full-size damage analysis

Subset-based DVC (ply level)

- Whole specimen
- Investigation of damage interaction

Z damage (transverse cracks)
X damage (delamination)
Y damage (split)

Detailed damage analysis

FE-based DVC (micro level)

Detailed damage analysis (crack analysis)

Ply-level volume of interest:
transverse ply – $220 \times 715 \times 1430 \mu\text{m}^3$

Ply-level crack analysis

Subset-based DVC

Ply-level crack analysis

Subset-based DVC

Strain profiles along the center-passing line

Micro-level crack analysis

FE-based DVC

Volume of interest:
from the transverse ply
 $220 \times 715 \times 275 \mu\text{m}^3$

Micro-level crack analysis

FE-based DVC

-8.00 30.85 69.70 (%)

E_{zz}

Micro-level crack analysis

FE-based DVC

Strain profiles along the center-passing line

Conclusions

- Both the virtual (digital) and real deformation showed that **DVC can measure strain** in 3D images of fiber-reinforced composites, acquired via synchrotron CT.
- The **virtual analysis** showed that:
 - ✓ even when the average displacement is calculated accurately, **strain concentrations** can appear at the edges and corners of the region of interest;
 - ✓ even when the calculated strain deviation is not very high, the resulting displacement can still be **inaccurate**;
 - ✓ the calculated average displacement for **longitudinal translation of the longitudinal ply** was most inaccurate, for **transverse translation of the longitudinal ply** was less inaccurate, and for both **longitudinal and transverse of the transverse ply** was most accurate.
- The cracks can be detected in DVC resulting strain by means of the (fake) **strain concentration** associated with their opening.
- Interactions between **damage mechanisms** can be explored via DVC.
- Further steps can be taken in addressing the **edge issue** in DVC and in better **quantification of damage**.

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MATERIALS ENGINEERING

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